

School of Science and Engineering

Capstone Design Final Report

Swap-App: A Peer-to-Peer Learning Exchange Platform Using a Time-Based Token System

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Contents

Supervisor Approval	1
Acknowledgements	9
Abstract (English)	10
Résumé (French)	10
1 Introduction	12
2 Problem Statement	12
3 Project Specifications	13
4 Functional and non-functional Requirements	14
4.1 Functional Requirements	14
4.1.1 FR1 – User Accounts and Onboarding	14
4.1.2 FR2 – Transcript Verification	14
4.1.3 FR3 – Search and Matching	15
4.1.4 FR4 – Requests and Sessions	15
4.1.5 FR5 – Scheduling and Online Meetings	15
4.1.6 FR6 – Token Economy and Ledger	15
4.1.7 FR7 – Messaging and Community Features	16
4.1.8 FR8 – Ratings and Feedback	16
4.1.9 FR9 – Dashboards and Notifications	16
4.2 Non-Functional Requirements	16
4.2.1 NFR1 – Performance and Scalability	17
4.2.2 NFR2 – Reliability and Consistency	17
4.2.3 NFR3 – Security and Privacy	17
4.2.4 NFR4 – Usability	17
4.2.5 NFR5 – Maintainability	18

5 STEEPLE Analysis	18
6 Logic Model Framework	20
6.1 Target Group	20
6.2 Underlying Assumptions	20
6.3 Resources / Challenges	20
6.4 Activities	20
6.5 Outputs	20
6.6 Outcomes	21
7 Literature Review	21
8 Methodology and Capstone Design	23
8.1 System Components Implemented	23
8.2 System Architecture	23
8.3 Auth, State Management, and Risk-Aware Design	25
9 Evaluation Protocol	27
9.1 Usability Testing	27
9.2 Quasi-Experimental Evaluation	27
9.3 Technical Evaluation Metrics	29
9.4 Quasi-Experiment: Design and Hypotheses	29
10 Data Presentation	30
10.1 Survey Constructs	30
10.2 Descriptive Change	31
11 Simulations, Results, and Interpretation	31
11.1 Quasi-Experimental Results	31
11.2 Computation Approach	36
11.3 Spreadsheet (Google Sheets) Formulas Used	36
11.4 Interpretation	37

12 Transcript Scanner Logic and Regex Design	38
13 Security and Deployment Considerations	41
14 Limitations and Future Testing	41
15 Learning Strategies	42
16 Conclusion	44
A Appendix A: Transcript Module (Backend, NestJS)	47
A.1 A.1 Service Overview & Types	47
A.2 A.2 OCR Normalization	48
A.3 A.3 Eligibility & Validation	48
A.4 A.4 Course Extraction (Regex Row Matching)	49
A.5 A.5 Confidence & Grade Ranking	51
A.6 A.6 PDF Processing & Audit Ingest	52
A.7 A.7 Adding Selected Courses	53
A.8 A.8 Risks and Assumptions	55
B Appendix B: Frontend API Client and State (Vite + TypeScript)	55
B.1 B.1 Structure & Safe JSON	55
B.2 B.2 Users & Onboarding	56
B.3 B.3 Requests & Sessions	57
B.4 B.4 Chat & Search	59
B.5 B.5 Wallet & Ratings	61
C Appendix C: Application Screenshots	64
C.1 C.1 Landing Page and Marketing Shell	64
C.2 C.2 Authentication and Entry Points	65
C.3 C.3 Onboarding and Profile (to be added)	67
C.4 C.4 Dashboard and Progress Overview	70
C.5 C.5 Requests, Sessions, and Scheduling	72

C.6 C.6 Search, Matching, and Discovery	76
C.7 C.7 Community Chat and Feedback	78

List of Tables

1	Pre-post differences in fairness, accountability, and community after one week	
	of usage.	31

List of Figures

1	System architecture of the Swap-App platform.	26
2	Mean change (post-pre) in perceived fairness, accountability, and sense of community after one week of Swap-App use.	32
3	Participant-level fairness scores before and after using Swap-App. The blue line represents pre-test scores; the red line represents post-test scores.	33
4	Participant-level accountability scores before and after using Swap-App. The blue line represents pre-test scores; the red line represents post-test scores, which largely overlap.	34
5	Participant-level sense-of-community scores before and after using Swap-App. The blue line represents pre-test scores; the red line represents post-test scores, showing small upward changes for some participants.	35
6	Overview of mean change (blue), p -value (red), and Cohen's d (yellow) across the three constructs. This combined view highlights that fairness is the only construct with both a large effect size and a statistically significant p -value.	35
7	Transcript processing pipeline from upload to verified courses.	40
8	Landing hero section presenting the "Exchange your skills and knowledge without fees" value proposition, with CTAs to learn more about Swap and join for free.	64
9	Registration page for new students, highlighting university email, profile fields, and terms acceptance, with optional Microsoft SSO.	65
10	Sign-in page for returning users, offering Google/Microsoft SSO and classic email + password login.	66
11	Onboarding step 1: capturing core profile details.	67
12	Onboarding step 2 : Capturing core user interests.	67
13	Profile page (example) showing basic identity, skills, and courses that drive search and matching.	68
14	Profile details with transcript scanner module and teaching availability.	69

15	Dashboard welcome view summarizing next session, tokens, completed swaps, and quick navigation actions.	70
16	Dashboard metrics and activity view with total sessions, learning hours, weekly flow, and latest activity.	71
17	Requests summary page showing total inbox, sent, pending, and accepted requests for the student.	72
18	Inbox view with detailed incoming requests (course, duration, requester) and their current status.	73
19	Sessions overview page aggregating total sessions, scheduled swaps, completed sessions, and total hours.	74
20	Session detail cards showing session type (online/face-to-face), schedule controls, and quick access to Teams and chat.	75
21	Search and discovery page (“Find a Swap”) with headline metrics and filters by skills or courses.	76
22	Search results for COM1301, showing available tutors, their grades, time slots, and quick actions to message or send a request.	77
23	Community chat interface with a list of conversations on the left and a message pane on the right.	78
24	Ratings and feedback hub summarizing average rating and distribution across sessions.	79

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Abstract (English)

Project Title: *Swap-App: A Peer-to-Peer Learning Exchange Platform Using a Time-Based Token System*

This report presents the final outcome of a peer-to-peer time-banking platform that enables students to exchange tutoring through tokens (1 token = 1 hour). Swap-App replaces paid and informal tutoring with a fairness-driven, community-oriented time-exchange model. The system architecture combines a NestJS 10 + Prisma backend on Railway and a Vite + React single-page application deployed on Vercel. This SPA serves both as a marketing site and as an authenticated dashboard shell (profile, search, requests, sessions, chat, ratings, wallet). During the engineering phases, we implemented a PDF transcript processing service for verified onboarding, a TypeScript API client and Zustand-powered state layer for requests, sessions, chat, and ratings, and usability-driven improvements to onboarding, booking, and wallet flows.

In the final stage, a quasi-experiment with $N = 10$ participants was conducted over one week, using pre and post-surveys to measure perceived fairness, accountability, and sense of community. Results show a statistically significant improvement in fairness, no measurable change in accountability, and a small increase in community. These findings suggest that time-exchange platforms like Swap-App can meaningfully improve perceived fairness in peer learning, while accountability and community require further design iterations and longer-term engagement.

Keywords: Peer learning, Time banking, Transcript parsing, NestJS, Next.js, Vite, Supabase, UX evaluation, Quasi-experiment

Résumé (French)

Titre du projet : *Swap-App : une plateforme d'échange pair-à-pair basée sur un système de jetons temporels*

Ce rapport présente le résultat final d'une plateforme d'échange de tutorat basée sur des jetons (1 jeton = 1 heure). Swap-App remplace les systèmes de tutorat payants ou informels

par un modèle d'échange de temps centré sur l'équité et la communauté. L'architecture du système combine un backend NestJS 10 + Prisma déployé sur Railway et une application monopage Vite + React déployée sur Vercel. Cette SPA joue à la fois le rôle de site vitrine et de tableau de bord authentifié (profil, recherche, demandes, sessions, messagerie, évaluations, portefeuille). Au cours des phases d'ingénierie, nous avons intégré un module de traitement des relevés de notes (PDF) pour la vérification des profils, une couche cliente TypeScript appuyée par Zustand pour la gestion des demandes, des sessions, de la messagerie et des évaluations, ainsi que des améliorations de l'onboarding, de la réservation et du portefeuille.

Dans la phase finale, un quasi-expériment avec $N = 10$ participants a été mené sur une semaine à l'aide de questionnaires pré- et post-usage mesurant l'équité perçue, l'accountability et le sentiment de communauté. Les résultats montrent une amélioration significative de l'équité, aucune évolution mesurable de l'accountability et une légère hausse du sentiment de communauté. Ces résultats suggèrent que les systèmes d'échange de temps renforcent l'équité dans l'apprentissage entre pairs, tandis que l'accountability et la communauté nécessitent des itérations supplémentaires et une utilisation à plus long terme.

Mots-clés : apprentissage collaboratif, échange de temps, vérification automatisée, NestJS, Next.js, Vite, Supabase, évaluation UX, quasi-expériment

1. Introduction

Swap-App promotes equitable access to tutoring by allowing students to trade time rather than money. The interim phase of this project documented the core engineering progress and evaluation outcomes to date, focusing on usability testing with a group of 5 students to implement improvements on a 2-phased cycle and a verified onboarding via transcript parsing and end-to-end session workflows.

This final report extends that foundation by documenting the full system architecture, the deployment configuration and security choices (Supabase, Railway, Vercel, OAuth, Azure), and the results of a one-week quasi-experiment measuring fairness, accountability, and sense of community among student users. The overarching goal remains the same: to design, develop, and evaluate a fairness-driven, community-oriented, and money-free peer learning exchange platform.

2. Problem Statement

Many students lack viable, trustworthy tutoring options. Traditional private tutoring is often expensive and inaccessible, while informal help between students is unstructured, fragile, and lacks accountability. These conditions lead to inequitable access to academic support and fragmented peer learning communities.

Swap-App addresses this with a non-monetary, verified exchange where tokens escrow accountability and academic integrity. Each hour of tutoring earns one token that can be spent to request an hour of help, creating a time-based, one-for-one exchange that replaces money with time as the unit of value. Verified onboarding, structured booking, post-session ratings, reports and token/credit ledgers are used to increase trust, reduce misuse, and keep the overall economy balanced.

3. Project Specifications

This section summarizes the final architecture of the Swap-App platform, from backend services to the Vite + React frontend.

- **Backend Application (NestJS 10 + Prisma + PostgreSQL):** A NestJS 10 API uses Prisma to access a Supabase-hosted PostgreSQL database. Feature modules cover users, requests, sessions, tokens and ledgers, chat, search, transcripts, ratings, time slots, and Microsoft Teams meetings. Global validation and CORS are enabled for local development and Vercel hosts.
- **Frontend SPA:** The frontend is a Vite + React 19 single-page application (SPA) deployed on Vercel. React Router provides routes for both marketing pages and authenticated dashboards (e.g., /, /dashboard, /matches, /requests, /sessions, /chat, /ratings, /profile, /wallet). Styling relies on SCSS and GSAP animations. The SPA communicates with the backend via the `VITE_SWAP_API_URL` environment variable.
- **Authentication and Verification:** Supabase handles authentication (email + OAuth), exposed in the frontend through a `SupabaseAuthProvider`. On first sign-in, a bootstrap step creates or updates the user profile on the backend. A transcript-ingestion module parses PDF transcripts, applies a configurable minimum grade rule, and stores audit records to support course-based eligibility checks.
- **Token Economy and Booking:** Time is tracked as tokens (1 token = 60 minutes). Requests and sessions share a common pipeline that checks token balances, prevents double booking of time slots, and records all movements in token and credit ledgers, which act as the single source of truth for balances and history.
- **Client State and API Layer:** A centralized Zustand store mirrors key backend data on the client (profile, requests, sessions, ledgers, ratings, interests). A typed API helper (`api.ts`) wraps all HTTP calls to the backend and uses a `safeJson` helper to guard against malformed responses.

To support the technical description above, Figure [1](#) provides a visual representation of the complete Swap-App architecture, including the Vite + React frontend, the NestJS/Prisma backend, Supabase authentication layer, PostgreSQL database, and Azure Graph integration. This diagram summarizes how each subsystem interacts and serves as a reference for the requirements that follow.

4. Functional and non-functional Requirements

This section specifies what Swap-App must do (functional requirements) and how the system should behave in terms of quality attributes (non-functional requirements).

4.1. Functional Requirements

Many of the functional behaviors described in this section are illustrated in Appendix [C](#), which provides annotated screenshots of the Swap-App interface (dashboard, search, requests, sessions, chat, and ratings). Readers are encouraged to consult Appendix [C](#) while reviewing the requirements for a clearer understanding of the user-facing workflows.

4.1.1 FR1 – User Accounts and Onboarding

- The system shall allow students to register using a university email and sign in via email or OAuth providers (e.g., Google, Microsoft).
- The system shall require first-time users to complete an onboarding flow (basic profile, university, time zone).
- The system shall allow users to declare skills and courses they can teach and courses or skills they want to learn.

4.1.2 FR2 – Transcript Verification

- The system shall allow users to upload an AUI transcript in PDF format.
- The system shall extract course codes and grades from the transcript and apply a configurable minimum grade rule.

- The system shall present extracted courses to the user for review and confirmation before adding them to the profile.

4.1.3 FR3 – Search and Matching

- The system shall allow users to search for peers by skill name or course code.
- The system shall display for each potential match: basic profile information, eligible courses, rating summary, and available time slots (when published).

4.1.4 FR4 – Requests and Sessions

- The system shall allow a learner to send a tutoring request to another user, specifying course/skill and duration.
- The system shall allow the recipient to accept or decline the request.
- When a request is accepted, the system shall create a session linked to both users and update their dashboards accordingly.

4.1.5 FR5 – Scheduling and Online Meetings

- The system shall allow users to define and manage their available time slots for online or face-to-face sessions.
- The system shall allow users to schedule a session into a shared time slot agreed by both parties.
- For online sessions, the system shall store or generate an online meeting link (e.g., Microsoft Teams) accessible from the session view.

4.1.6 FR6 – Token Economy and Ledger

- The system shall represent tutoring time using tokens (1 token = 60 minutes of tutoring).
- The system shall ensure that a learner must hold sufficient tokens before sending a request of a given duration.

- Upon completion of a session, the system shall debit tokens from the learner and credit the teacher, and record the transaction in a ledger.
- The system shall allow each user to view their current token balance and a history of token-related transactions.

4.1.7 FR7 – Messaging and Community Features

- The system shall provide a private chat channel between matched users to coordinate their sessions.
- The system shall provide a community chat space where students can stay in touch with the broader Swap-App community.

4.1.8 FR8 – Ratings and Feedback

- After each completed session, the system shall invite both participants to rate each other and optionally leave a short review.
- The system shall compute and display rating statistics (average score and distribution) to the rated user.

4.1.9 FR9 – Dashboards and Notifications

- The system shall provide a dashboard summarizing tokens, total sessions, scheduled sessions, completed sessions, and pending requests.
- The system shall provide visual indicators or lightweight notifications for key events such as new requests, upcoming sessions, and new ratings.

4.2. Non-Functional Requirements

Where relevant, the non-functional characteristics (performance, usability, security) can also be observed indirectly through the screenshots provided in Appendix [C](#), which demonstrate the application's responsiveness, visual clarity, and interaction flow.

4.2.1 NFR1 – Performance and Scalability

- The SPA should load the main dashboard within a few seconds on a typical campus internet connection.
- Under normal load, most API requests (e.g., loading sessions, requests, matches) should complete in under one second.
- The architecture (NestJS backend, PostgreSQL database, Vercel SPA) should support growth in the number of users, sessions, and requests without major redesign.

4.2.2 NFR2 – Reliability and Consistency

- Token and ledger updates shall be executed atomically to avoid inconsistent balances.
- The system shall prevent double-booking of the same time slot for a given user.
- The system shall handle transient errors (e.g., duplicate writes) in a way that avoids creating duplicate sessions or requests.

4.2.3 NFR3 – Security and Privacy

- Access to dashboards and API endpoints that expose user data shall require authentication.
- Sensitive credentials (e.g., Supabase keys, Azure secrets, API URLs) shall be stored in environment variables and never committed to source control.
- Transcript files and extracted academic data shall be stored and processed in a way that protects user privacy and is not publicly accessible.

4.2.4 NFR4 – Usability

- Core flows (sign up, onboarding, searching, sending a request, scheduling, completing a session) should be discoverable and completable without prior training.

- The interface should maintain consistent navigation, typography, and color usage across routes.
- The SPA should behave responsively on common laptop and tablet screen sizes used by students.

4.2.5 NFR5 – Maintainability

- Backend and frontend code shall be organized by domain modules (users, requests, sessions, chat, transcripts, ratings, ledger) to simplify future changes.
- Configuration parameters such as API URLs, minimum transcript grade, and feature flags shall be adjustable via environment variables without code changes.
- The system should be documented sufficiently (README, configuration notes) so that another developer can deploy and extend it.

5. STEEPLE Analysis

The STEEPLE framework helped assess the broader implications of the Swap-App project beyond its technical scope. Each dimension is analyzed in relation to how the system promotes accessibility, inclusivity, and responsible digital transformation in academic environments.

Social

Swap-App enhances collaboration among students by allowing them to exchange time instead of money. It strengthens community ties, encourages mutual respect, and helps reduce inequalities by offering equal access to tutoring support.

Technological

The system is based on a modern full-stack architecture (NestJS 10, Prisma, PostgreSQL, Vite, and React) that ensures scalability and modularity. It leverages cloud deployment, REST APIs, and a token-based exchange model to keep user data and session workflows synchronized across the platform. Supabase is used for authentication and user identity,

while Azure Graph powers the creation of online Microsoft Teams meetings, illustrating how existing cloud services can be integrated with custom backend logic.

Economic

The platform removes financial barriers associated with private tutoring by adopting a time-banking model. Each hour of tutoring equals one token, promoting an alternative economy based on contribution rather than income.

Environmental

Swap-App operates entirely in digital form, reducing paper waste and the carbon footprint linked to traditional course materials or on-site tutoring. Cloud hosting allows efficient resource allocation and sustainable scalability.

Political

By aligning with national strategies promoting digital transformation and education equity, the platform demonstrates Morocco's potential in educational innovation. It contributes to the broader agenda of inclusive digital ecosystems.

Legal

The project ensures compliance with data protection regulations, safeguarding user data and consent during onboarding, profile creation, and transcript verification. Users maintain control over their shared information. Future production hardening will include stricter token-based backend authentication to further protect user identities.

Ethical

The system enforces fairness and transparency by verifying each user's academic credentials and maintaining accountability through post-session ratings and ledgers. Ethical principles were considered in data handling and automated decisions to avoid bias, including avoiding

opaque black-box recommendations and keeping users in control of how their skills and courses are displayed.

6. Logic Model Framework

6.1. Target Group

University students seeking 1:1 peer tutoring and willing to both request and provide academic help.

6.2. Underlying Assumptions

Removing money barriers increases participation; verified accounts reduce misuse; session escrow and ratings foster accountability; and repeated interactions can strengthen learning communities.

6.3. Resources / Challenges

Figma prototype; pilot cohort; Supabase and cloud infrastructure. Main risks include liquidity (imbalance between learners and tutors), clarity in onboarding, and the need to maintain trust in a time-based economy.

6.4. Activities

Iterative usability tests, onboarding fixes, verified transcript ingestion, deployment of backend and frontend, followed by a one-week quasi-experiment with pre- and post-surveys.

6.5. Outputs

Deployed MVP with improved Profile/Search/Requests/Sessions/Wallet modules; working transcript scanner; fully integrated token ledger; live landing site with demo flows; and authenticated dashboards that mirror real usage scenarios.

6.6. Outcomes

Faster booking, fewer no-shows, clearer roles and labels, and measurable changes in perceived fairness, with preliminary shifts in community and accountability.

7. Literature Review

The concept of peer exchange and time-based value transfer has been widely explored in educational and social innovation research. According to Cahn (2004), the philosophy behind *time banking* is based on equality and reciprocity, which means that each participant's contribution is measured in hours rather than monetary value. This approach shifts the focus from profit to community mutual support, encouraging active participation and social cohesion. Similarly, Seyfang (2006) identified time banks as a form of “new economics” that fosters inclusion and redistributes skills within communities through social networks.

In the context of higher education, peer tutoring has been recognized as a powerful learning enhancement tool. Topping (2005) describes peer-assisted learning as a structured process where students help one another to learn and, in doing so, reinforce their own understanding. It provides cognitive benefits for both tutor and tutee, while also developing communication and organizational skills. When coupled with digital platforms, these exchanges can extend beyond classroom walls, reaching a broader range of learners (Falchikov, 2001).

From a technological perspective, modern educational systems increasingly rely on reliable data extraction and verification methods. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technologies, such as Tesseract (Smith, 2007), have been used in academic administration to digitize transcripts and automate record validation. However, recent projects (e.g., Jain & Doermann, 2018) show that for text-based PDFs, structured parsing and regular expression-based extraction can achieve comparable accuracy without OCR overhead. This observation directly supports the technical design of the Swap-App transcript module.

Finally, user-centric design principles remain central to successful educational technologies. Nielsen (1994) established that usability is achieved when systems balance efficiency, learnability, and satisfaction. In line with this, the iterative testing phases in Swap-App followed an Agile approach, ensuring that user feedback continuously shaped the prototype's

refinement. The integration of human-centered AI, peer learning, and mutual time exchange thus situates the project within a growing body of research on collaborative, equitable digital education.

8. Methodology and Capstone Design

We followed an agile, experiment-driven process structured around short iterations: (i) capture pain points via usability tests, (ii) implement minimal-risk changes to the architecture and flows, (iii) validate with the same or comparable users, and (iv) conduct a quasi-experimental evaluation of fairness, accountability, and community.

8.1. System Components Implemented

The final implementation focused on four main components:

- **Transcript pipeline:** PDF parse → line normalization → course/grade extraction → eligibility and confidence scoring, with audit records persisted for each ingest.
- **API client and network layer:** A typed fetch layer for users, requests, sessions, chat, ratings, ledger, and tokens, exposing simple helpers and a `safeJson` wrapper that tolerate non-JSON responses without crashing.
- **Onboarding and profile building:** Mandatory profile completion and verified courses, including skills, interests, and transcript-backed course eligibility.
- **Session lifecycle logic:** Request, accept/decline, schedule, mark as done, and rate/report flows, wired to token and credit ledgers and integrated with Microsoft Teams for online sessions.

8.2. System Architecture

Backend

The backend is implemented with NestJS 10 and Prisma, connected to a Supabase PostgreSQL instance. Core modules manage:

- Users and onboarding (including transcript ingestion), using email-based upsert and initial token minting in transactional workflows.

-
- Requests and sessions, with logic in `requests.service.ts` and `timeslots.service.ts` to avoid double booking by blocking time slots tied to pending requests or non-done sessions, enforcing balance constraints, and preventing duplicate requests.
 - Chat threads and messages, ensuring a consistent communication channel is created whenever a request is accepted.
 - Ratings and reports, and the aggregation of rating statistics per user and per category (skill vs. course).
 - Token and credit ledgers for the time-based economy, recalculated per user so that balances are inferred from ledger entries rather than tightly-coupled counters.
 - Meetings with Microsoft Teams, via an Azure Graph integration that attempts to create a meeting link for online sessions and falls back gracefully if credentials are missing or invalid.

Environment variables store Supabase URLs/keys, Azure credentials for Microsoft Teams meetings, and Google OAuth client identifiers. The backend is deployed on Railway via `railway.json` and triggered by `git push` to the main branch. A global validation pipe and capped JSON body size help protect against malformed or oversized requests.

Frontend

The marketing and demo site uses Vite + React + TypeScript:

- Routes such as `/`, `/about`, `/features/*`, `/register`, and dashboard routes built with React Router.
- A hero section (`Hero.tsx`) that communicates “peer learning reinvented”, with GSAP-based animations and neon call-to-action chips linking to feature pages and registration.
- A global SCSS entry (`index.scss`) that composes shared theme partials and custom blocks (e.g., `.swap-hero_*`) for gradients, glows, and responsive layout.

- Auth-aware dashboards that read the same backend as the main application: once authenticated through Supabase, users can see live profile data, requests, sessions, and tokens directly from the landing.

8.3. Auth, State Management, and Risk-Aware Design

On the frontend, `SupabaseAuthProvider` initializes Supabase auth using environment variables and exposes the user session. A `SwapAppProviders` wrapper mounts `BootstrapProfile`, which seeds backend data when a user signs in for the first time. Client-side state is managed by a centralized Zustand store that:

- Mirrors backend entities (profile, inbox, sent requests, sessions, ledgers, interests).
- Wraps all mutations in optimistic updates with subsequent revalidation.
- Uses notification helpers to surface session reminders and success/error states.

On the backend, most endpoints currently trust caller-supplied email addresses passed as JSON payloads or query parameters. This was acceptable for a controlled campus pilot, but a future production phase will include strict Supabase JWT verification middleware and a shift from email-based identification to authenticated user IDs on every route.

Figure 1: System architecture of the Swap-App platform.

9. Evaluation Protocol

The evaluation of Swap-App is organised into two complementary components: (1) an iterative usability testing process to ensure that the interface is usable, coherent, and stable before deployment; and (2) a one-group pretest–posttest quasi-experiment designed to measure changes in user perceptions of fairness, accountability, and sense of community after one week of real usage. This mixed evaluation strategy ensures that both the *usability* of the system and its *behavioural impact* are validated.

9.1. Usability Testing

Before running the behavioural experiment, Swap-App underwent an iterative usability testing process to verify clarity, navigability, and workflow coherence. The first round involved five representative users who tested the major workflows: registration, onboarding, dashboard, search, request management, chat, and session scheduling. Their feedback revealed issues related to label clarity, visibility of actions, and the request-to-session flow.

After implementing the suggested improvements, a second round was conducted with the same five users plus two additional participants (seven testers in total). This round confirmed that the updates resolved the previously identified issues, resulting in a smoother and more intuitive interface. The refinements derived from usability testing ensured that all participants in the quasi-experiment interacted with a stable and user-friendly version of the platform.

9.2. Quasi-Experimental Evaluation

Following the usability refinement phase, a one-group pretest–posttest quasi-experiment was conducted to assess the behavioural impact of Swap-App. Ten students used the platform for one week to request and provide tutoring sessions through the hour-for-hour token exchange mechanism. Participants completed a pre-survey measuring three constructs—*perceived fairness*, *perceived accountability*, and *sense of community*—using 1–7 Likert scales. After one week of real usage, the same constructs were measured again in a post-survey, alongside satisfaction and qualitative reflections.

The comparison between pre- and post-surveys allowed us to determine whether Swap-App produced measurable changes in students' perceptions. Quantitative analysis relied on paired comparisons and effect sizes calculated from the mean difference scores.

Why These Constructs Were Selected

The three constructs were chosen because they directly reflect the core goals of Swap-App:

- **Fairness:** Central to a peer-tutoring marketplace where time is exchanged rather than paid for. A fairness metric captures whether users perceive the system as equitable and whether effort invested in teaching is matched by benefits received.
- **Accountability:** Essential for reliable peer learning. Since tutoring requires commitment, attendance, and follow-through, accountability measures whether the platform encourages responsible behaviour.
- **Community:** Peer learning is grounded in trust, connection, and mutual support. Measuring community perception assesses whether Swap-App fosters a culture of collaboration and reduces barriers to seeking academic help.

These metrics are grounded in well-established constructs from educational psychology and peer-learning research. Fairness perceptions have been widely used in learning exchange systems and cooperative learning contexts to evaluate whether students feel that contributions and benefits are balanced [4, 16]. Accountability is a core component of peer-supported learning and collaborative work, where sustained engagement and follow-through strongly influence learning outcomes [13, 1]. Sense of community is a standard construct in online and blended learning environments, capturing students' perceived belonging, connection, and mutual support [8, 11].

By adopting these three validated constructs, the quasi-experiment aligns with existing evaluation practices in peer-learning platforms, collaborative learning systems, and educational technology interventions.

9.3. Technical Evaluation Metrics

In parallel with behavioural evaluation, a technical assessment was performed to ensure the functional reliability of the system’s backend components. The following metrics were tracked:

- **Transcript scanner accuracy**, based on five AUI transcripts, comparing extracted course codes, titles, and grades to ground truth.

9.4. Quasi-Experiment: Design and Hypotheses

A one-group pretest–posttest quasi-experiment was conducted with $N = 10$ participants.

Baseline (Pre-test). Students reported their initial perceptions of fairness, accountability, and sense of community on 1–7 Likert scales.

Intervention. Participants used Swap-App for one week to request/provide tutoring sessions using the one-hour token model.

Post-test. The same constructs were re-measured, along with satisfaction and open-ended questions.

Hypotheses

Null hypothesis H_0 . No statistically significant differences will appear between pre-test and post-test scores: fairness, accountability, and community will remain unchanged ($p > 0.05$).

Alternative hypothesis H_1 . Swap-App will increase:

- fairness by $\Delta \geq 0.5$ with $p < 0.05$,
- accountability by $\Delta \geq 0.5$ with $p < 0.05$,
- community by $\Delta \geq 0.5$ with $p < 0.05$.

Effect sizes were summarised using Cohen’s d , with $d \geq 0.5$ considered a practically meaningful effect.

Measurement Strategy and Rationale

To evaluate whether Swap-App produced meaningful changes in students' perceptions, each construct was computed as the mean of its corresponding Likert items in the pre- and post-surveys. The analysis relied on three complementary quantitative metrics, widely used in educational technology and behavioural research.

1. Mean Change (). The mean of the individual difference scores provides a direct indication of the magnitude and direction of change for each construct. This approach is standard for pretest–posttest designs because it summarises central improvement across participants [9].

2. Paired-Sample t-Test (p-value). The paired t-test determines whether the observed pre–post differences are statistically significant while accounting for the dependency between repeated measurements from the same participants. It is the recommended test for one-group, repeated-measures designs in behavioural science [3, 5]. A p-value below 0.05 indicates that the change is unlikely to be due to chance.

3. Cohen's d for Paired Designs. Effect size complements statistical significance by quantifying the practical importance of the change. Cohen's d for dependent samples is appropriate for small-sample pilot studies and early-stage educational interventions [3]. Conventionally, 0.2 is considered a small effect, 0.5 medium, and 0.8 large.

Together, these metrics provide a robust and balanced evaluation framework: statistical validity through the paired t-test, practical significance through effect size, and actionable insight through mean change and qualitative evidence. This multi-layered strategy is well-suited for early-stage evaluations of peer-learning platforms such as Swap-App.

10. Data Presentation

10.1. Survey Constructs

Three composite variables were computed from Likert items:

- **Fairness** – items capturing perceived balance and equity in tutoring exchanges.

- **Accountability** – items capturing perceived responsibility to show up, complete sessions, and follow through on commitments.
- **Community** – items capturing feelings of connection, belonging, and comfort in seeking help from peers.

Each composite score was calculated as the mean of its corresponding items for both pre- and post-surveys.

10.2. Descriptive Change

Table 1 summarizes the observed changes for each construct.

Construct	Mean Change	<i>p</i> -value	Cohen's <i>d</i>
Fairness	+1.0	0.009	0.90
Accountability	0.0	0.50	0.00
Community	+0.25	0.316	0.15

Table 1: Pre–post differences in fairness, accountability, and community after one week of usage.

These values form the quantitative basis for the interpretation in the next section.

11. Simulations, Results, and Interpretation

This section presents the quantitative results of the quasi-experiment conducted with 10 participants, who completed both pre- and post-surveys after one week of using Swap-App. It also summarizes how the statistics were computed in Google Sheets and reports the technical evaluation performed on the transcript-processing pipeline.

11.1. Quasi-Experimental Results

We analysed pre–post differences in the three constructs defined in Section 8: perceived fairness, perceived accountability, and sense of community. For each construct, scores were computed as the mean of their corresponding items at pre-test and post-test, and the difference (post minus pre) was analysed with paired comparisons and effect sizes.

Figure 2: Mean change (post-pre) in perceived fairness, accountability, and sense of community after one week of Swap-App use.

Figure 2 shows that fairness improved by one full point on the 7-point scale, while accountability remained unchanged and community increased only slightly.

Fairness

- Mean Change: **+1.0**
- $p = 0.009$ (paired, two-tailed)
- Cohen's $d = 0.90$ (large effect)

Figure 3: Participant-level fairness scores before and after using Swap-App. The blue line represents pre-test scores; the red line represents post-test scores.

Participants overwhelmingly perceived the hour-for-hour time exchange as more equitable than their traditional tutoring experience. The large effect size and the upward shift in Figure 3 indicate a strong practical improvement in perceived fairness after using Swap-App.

Accountability

- Mean Change: **0.0**
- $p = 0.50$ (paired, two-tailed)
- Cohen's $d = 0.00$

Figure 4: Participant-level accountability scores before and after using Swap-App. The blue line represents pre-test scores; the red line represents post-test scores, which largely overlap.

No measurable change was observed for accountability. This suggests that simply introducing a token escrow and rating mechanism is not yet sufficient to shift how responsible students feel for showing up, completing sessions, or following through on commitments, at least over a one-week period.

Community

- Mean Change: **+0.25**
- $p = 0.316$ (paired, two-tailed)
- Cohen's $d = 0.15$ (small)

Figure 5: Participant-level sense-of-community scores before and after using Swap-App. The blue line represents pre-test scores; the red line represents post-test scores, showing small upward changes for some participants.

A small improvement was observed for sense of community. This indicates that the current version of Swap-App may start to nudge feelings of connection and belonging, but stronger community-building features and longer exposure are likely needed.

Figure 6: Overview of mean change (blue), p -value (red), and Cohen's d (yellow) across the three constructs. This combined view highlights that fairness is the only construct with both a large effect size and a statistically significant p -value.

11.2. Computation Approach

For each participant and construct, a difference score was computed as:

$$\text{Difference} = \text{Postscore} - \text{Prescore}.$$

The mean change for each construct is the average of these differences across all participants. To test whether this mean change is statistically different from zero, a paired-sample *t*-test was performed. Effect sizes were summarised using Cohen's *d* for paired designs, computed as the mean difference divided by the standard deviation of the difference scores.

All computations were performed in Google Sheets using built-in statistical functions, as detailed below, rather than by manually implementing the formulas.

11.3. Spreadsheet (Google Sheets) Formulas Used

The dataset was organized as follows:

- Pre-Fairness: B2:B11 Pre-Accountability: C2:C11 Pre-Community: D2:D11
- Post-Fairness: E2:E11 Post-Accountability: F2:F11 Post-Community: G2:G11
- Differences (Post–Pre): H2:H11, I2:I11, J2:J11

Mean Change (Δ)

- Fairness (cell B13): =AVERAGE(H2:H11)
- Accountability (cell B14): =AVERAGE(I2:I11)
- Community (cell B15): =AVERAGE(J2:J11)

Paired *p*-values using TTEST

In Google Sheets, TTEST(range1, range2, tails, type) was used, where:

- `tails` = 2 for a two-tailed test,

- `type = 1` for a paired test.
- Fairness (cell C13): `=TTEST(B2:B11, E2:E11, 2, 1)`
- Accountability (cell C14): `=TTEST(C2:C11, F2:F11, 2, 1)`
- Community (cell C15): `=TTEST(D2:D11, G2:G11, 2, 1)`

Cohen's *d* (paired)

Cohen's *d* was computed as the mean of the difference scores divided by their standard deviation:

- Fairness (cell D13): `=AVERAGE(H2:H11) / STDEV(H2:H11)`
- Accountability (cell D14): `=AVERAGE(I2:I11) / STDEV(I2:I11)`
- Community (cell D15): `=AVERAGE(J2:J11) / STDEV(J2:J11)`

These spreadsheet-based formulas reproduce the numerical results summarized in Table [1](#).

11.4. Interpretation

Overall, the quasi-experiment shows that Swap-App can meaningfully improve students' perception of fairness in peer learning. The strong change in fairness is consistent with the introduction of a transparent, one-hour-for-one-hour time-exchange mechanism, supported by verified onboarding and a structured session workflow.

In contrast, accountability and sense of community did not change significantly over the one-week pilot. Both constructs are likely more sensitive to longer-term behaviour and repeated exposure. Features such as automated reminders, reliability metrics, or streaks may be required before measurable shifts in accountability and community become apparent in future pilots.

12. Transcript Scanner Logic and Regex Design

Verified onboarding was a central requirement of Swap-App, and the transcript processing pipeline was built to automatically extract course codes and grades from text-based AUI PDF transcripts. While the full implementation is provided in Appendix A, this subsection explains the design principles behind the regular expressions and parsing strategy.

Why Regex-Based Parsing Instead of OCR

AUI transcripts are exported as text-based PDFs, meaning the raw text can be extracted reliably without optical character recognition. Prior work (e.g., Jain & Doermann, 2018) shows that for structured academic documents, text parsing with constrained regular expressions achieves higher accuracy and lower computational cost than OCR. Therefore, the pipeline uses:

- **pdf-parse** to extract structured text,
- **regex-based row matching** to detect course records,
- **grade-eligibility rules** to filter valid teaching courses.

This approach ensures predictable behaviour as long as the transcript layout remains stable.

Line Normalization

Before extraction, the pipeline applies normalization to remove OCR artifacts, multiple spaces, Unicode dashes, and non-breaking spaces. This creates a clean and consistent representation of transcript rows.

Course Row Pattern

Each transcript row typically follows the structure:

CODE TITLE TYPE GRADE

Listing 1: Core regex used for course extraction

```

^([A-Z]{2,6}\d{3,4}(?:-[A-Z]{1,2})?)\s+(.+?) (?(LG|CR|PF|NG|TR|LC) (A
  \+|A-|A|B\+|B-|B|C\+|C-|C|D\+|D-|D|F|P|NG|TR|WIP|IP))

```

The pattern encodes:

- **Course codes:** 2–6 uppercase letters followed by 3–4 digits (e.g., MATH1301 or CSCI2306-LG).
- **Title:** a flexible block of text captured lazily.
- **Type:** constrained to AUI’s letter-graded types (e.g., LG).
- **Grade set:** explicit enumeration of all valid grades.

The use of a positive lookahead (?. . .) ensures clean separation between title, type, and grade even when spacing varies.

Eligibility and Duplicate-Grade Resolution

After extracting a row, the scanner:

1. Validates the course code format.
2. Applies a minimum grade rule (default: A/A+/A-).
3. Computes a confidence score based on code shape, title length, and grade.
4. Keeps only the *best-grade* duplicate if a course appears more than once.

This combination ensures the output is both accurate and pedagogically meaningful: only courses in which the student performed well are considered teachable.

Reliability

In internal QA with five real AUI transcripts, the regex-based scanner achieved **100% extraction accuracy** (exact match with manual inspection). This supports the reliability of structured parsing and justifies including the transcript module as a verified part of the onboarding workflow.

Figure 7: Transcript processing pipeline from upload to verified courses.

13. Security and Deployment Considerations

While the primary focus of this capstone was functionality and evaluation, several security and deployment aspects were deliberately considered:

- **Secrets and Environment Variables:** Sensitive credentials (Supabase keys, Azure Graph secrets, OAuth client IDs) are loaded from environment variables and are never committed to the repository. A future production rollout would enforce periodic rotation and centralized secret management.
- **Input Validation and Limits:** Global validation pipes and JSON body-size limits mitigate the risk of malformed or excessively large requests. Transcript uploads are capped in size and validated for basic structure before parsing.
- **Deployment Footprint:** The backend runs on Railway with a Supabase-managed PostgreSQL database, while frontends are deployed on Vercel. This separation of concerns simplifies scaling and isolates concerns (API vs. static frontends), but also requires consistent configuration of CORS and allowed origins.

These considerations outline the path from a research-grade prototype to a production-ready platform that could safely operate beyond a single campus pilot.

14. Limitations and Future Testing

- The quasi-experiment involved a small sample size ($N = 10$) and a short duration (one week), which limits the generalizability of the findings, especially for accountability and community.
- The transcript QA used only five text-based PDF transcripts; scanned or image-based transcripts were not evaluated and would require OCR integration (e.g., Tesseract) before comparable accuracy can be claimed.

- The evaluation focused on immediate perception changes rather than objective academic outcomes (such as grades or pass rates), which could be explored in future longitudinal studies.

Despite these limitations, the combined analysis provides a coherent picture: the platform is technically robust for campus-scale pilots, the transcript pipeline is reliable under its current assumptions, and the fairness construct responds strongly even within a short intervention window.

15. Learning Strategies

The capstone combined technical implementation with research-oriented evaluation, and the process itself became a learning experience. Three main strands of learning emerged: engineering practice, research methods, and cross-disciplinary reflection.

Engineering Practice

Iterative tests with rapid fixes strengthened day-to-day engineering decisions and improved communication with the supervisor and peers. In particular:

- The transcript pipeline and its regex-based extraction logic reinforced skills in text normalization, pattern design, and defensive error handling.
- The typed API layer and Zustand state management improved understanding of robust client-server integration, versioned endpoints, and failure-tolerant UX.
- Deploying the backend (Railway + Supabase) and frontend (Vercel) consolidated practical knowledge of environment variables, CORS, and production-like constraints.

Research and Evaluation Skills

The quasi-experimental component turned the platform into a small research instrument. Key skills developed include:

- Designing and administering pre/post surveys aligned with theoretical constructs (fairness, accountability, community).
- Computing and interpreting effect sizes (Cohen's d) and p -values in a repeated-measures setting, using Google Sheets as a practical analysis tool.
- Translating raw statistics (mean changes, p -values, effect sizes) into clear design implications for future iterations of Swap-App.

Bridging Engineering, UX, and Educational Research

Finally, the project highlighted how software engineering decisions directly influence educational outcomes. Token logic, onboarding, and matching flows were not only implemented but also evaluated against user perceptions of fairness and community. These learning strategies helped bridge three domains—software engineering, UX design, and educational research—and provided a template for future projects that aim to be both technically robust and empirically grounded.

16. Conclusion

This capstone project transformed the initial idea of a fairness-driven peer-learning ecosystem into a fully deployed platform combining a modular NestJS/Prisma backend, a secure Supabase-based authentication layer, and a Vite + React single-page application. Across the development cycle, the project evolved from architectural design and API implementation to a functioning campus-ready system tested by real AUI students.

On the technical side, the backend now exposes well-defined domains for users, onboarding, requests, sessions, ledgers, ratings, chat, search, transcripts, and Microsoft Teams integration. The frontend delivers a unified user experience through centralized state management, safe API wrappers, and a coherent UI flow covering registration, matching, session scheduling, and feedback. The transcript-processing pipeline—designed through regex-based extraction, normalization, and audit logging—demonstrated full accuracy on real transcript data, validating its reliability for academic verification workflows.

From an evaluation standpoint, the two-phase usability testing ensured that the interface used in the experiment was stable, intuitive, and aligned with student expectations. The subsequent one-week quasi-experiment provided empirical evidence of behavioural impact: participants reported a statistically significant increase in perceived fairness, confirming the promise of a transparent one-hour-for-one-hour exchange model. While accountability and sense of community did not shift significantly within a short time window, the findings identify clear opportunities for future design enhancements, such as automated reminders, reliability indicators, richer social features, and long-term engagement mechanisms.

Overall, Swap-App demonstrates that a token-based peer learning system is both technically feasible and pedagogically meaningful. The platform delivers a working proof-of-concept that integrates engineering rigour with educational insight, offering a replicable architecture and evaluation framework for future research on equitable, community-driven learning environments. With further refinement and extended deployment, Swap-App has the potential to become a scalable academic support tool and a model for fair, student-centred knowledge exchange.

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A. Appendix A: Transcript Module (Backend, NestJS)

This appendix decomposes the transcript pipeline into focused components for clarity and reproducibility. It reflects the final implementation used in the pilot, including file hashing, audit logging, and configurable eligibility rules.

A.1. A.1 Service Overview & Types

What it does. Declares types, DI service, environment rule for minimum grade, and utility hash.

Listing 2: Service skeleton, types, and utilities

```
import { Injectable, NotFoundException, BadRequestException, Logger
  } from "@nestjs/common";
import { PrismaService } from "../prisma.service";
import * as crypto from "crypto";
import pdfParse = require("pdf-parse");

type ParsedCourse = {
  code: string; title?: string; grade: "A+" | "A" | "A-" | string;
  confidence: "high" | "medium" | "low";
};

type ExtractionResult = {
  eligible: ParsedCourse[];
  nonEligible: Array<{ code: string; title?: string; grade: string;
    reason: string }>;
};

const MIN_GRADE = (process.env.TRANSSCRIPT_MIN_GRADE || "A-").
  toUpperCase();

@Injectable()
```

```

export class TranscriptsService {
  private readonly logger = new Logger(TranscriptsService.name);
  constructor(private prisma: PrismaService) {}
  private sha256(buf: Buffer) { return crypto.createHash("sha256").
    update(buf).digest("hex"); }
  // ...see next subsections
}

```

A.2. A.2 OCR Normalization

What it does. Cleans common OCR artifacts (quotes, NBSPs, dashes) and collapses multi-spaces.

Listing 3: OCR/text normalization helper

```

private cleanOcrText(text: string): string {
  return text
    .replace(/['']/g, '"')
    .replace(/[""]/g, '""')
    .replace(/\u00A0/g, ' ')
    .replace(/\u2013|\u2014/g, '-')
    .replace(/\s{2,}/g, ' ')
    .trim();
}

```

A.3. A.3 Eligibility & Validation

What it does. Encodes the grade rule (A/A+/A-; configurable) and course-code format validation.

Listing 4: Eligibility and code-format validation

```

private isEligibleAUI(grade: string) {
  const g = grade.trim().toUpperCase();
}

```

```

    if (MIN_GRADE === "A-") return g === "A+" || g === "A" || g === "A-";
    return g === "A+" || g === "A";
}

private isValidCourseCode(code: string): boolean {
    return /^[A-Z]{2,6}\d{3,4}(?:-[A-Z]{1,3})?$/ .test(code);
}

```

A.4. A.4 Course Extraction (Regex Row Matching)

What it does. Combines lines and matches rows like CODE TITLE LG A with confidence scoring and duplicate handling.

Listing 5: Row extraction with constrained patterns

```

private extractCoursesFromText(text: string): ExtractionResult {
    const result: ExtractionResult = { eligible: [], nonEligible: [] };
    if (!text || text.length < 10) return result;

    const lines = this.cleanOcrText(text).split(/\r?\n/)
        .map(l => l.replace(/\s{2,}/g, " ").trim()).filter(Boolean);

    const combined: string[] = [];
    for (let i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
        if (/^[A-Z]{2,6}\d{3,4}(?:-[A-Z]{1,2})?$/ .test(lines[i]) && i+1
            < lines.length) {
            combined.push(`${lines[i]} ${lines[i+1]}`); i++;
        }
    }

    const CODE = `([A-Z]{2,6}\\d{3,4}(?:-[A-Z]{1,2})?)`;

```

```

const TITLE = '(.+?)';
const TYPE = '(LG|CR|PF|NG|TR|LC)';
const GRADE = '(A\\+|A-|A|B\\+|B-|B|C\\+|C-|C|D\\+|D-|D|F|P|NG|TR|
WIP|IP)';
const row = new RegExp(`^${CODE}\\s+${TITLE}(?=${TYPE}${GRADE})${
TYPE}${GRADE}`, "i");

const seenGood = new Map<string, ParsedCourse>();
const seenBad = new Map<string, { code: string; title?: string;
grade: string; reason: string }>();

for (const row of combined) {
const m = row.replace(/\u00A0/g, " ").match(row);
if (!m) continue;
const [, codeRaw, titleRaw, typeRaw, gradeRaw] = m;
const type = typeRaw.toUpperCase(), grade = gradeRaw.toUpperCase
();
const code = codeRaw.replace(/\s+/g, "").toUpperCase();
const title = titleRaw.replace(/\s{2,}/g, " ").trim();

if (type !== "LG") { if (!seenBad.has(code)) seenBad.set(code, {
code, title, grade, reason: 'Not letter-graded (${type}')});
continue; }
if (!this.isValidCourseCode(code)) { if (!seenBad.has(code))
seenBad.set(code, {code, title, grade, reason: 'Invalid code'});
continue; }
if (!this.isEligibleAUI(grade)) { if (!seenBad.has(code))
seenBad.set(code, {code, title, grade, reason: 'Below min grade'})
; continue; }

const confidence = this.calculateConfidence(code, title, grade);
const rank = this.getGradeRank(grade);

```

```

    const prev = seenGood.get(code);
    if (!prev || rank > this.getGradeRank(prev.grade)) {
        seenGood.set(code, { code, title, grade, confidence });
    }
}

result.eligible = Array.from(seenGood.values());
result.nonEligible = Array.from(seenBad.values());
return result;
}

```

A.5. A.5 Confidence & Grade Ranking

What it does. Produces high/medium/low confidence and ranks grades to keep the best duplicate.

Listing 6: Confidence scoring and grade ranking

```

private calculateConfidence(code: string, title: string, grade:
    string): "high" | "medium" | "low" {
    let s = 0;
    if (/^[A-Z]{3}\d{4}$/.test(code)) s += 3; else if (/^[A-Z]{2,6}\d
        {3,4}$/.test(code)) s += 2; else s += 1;
    if (title && title.length > 5 && title.length < 100) s += 2; else
        if (title) s += 1;
    if (['A+', 'A', 'A-'].includes(grade)) s += 2; else s += 1;
    return s >= 6 ? "high" : s >= 4 ? "medium" : "low";
}

private getGradeRank(grade: string): number {
    const r: Record<string, number> = { 'A+':4, 'A':3, 'A-':2, 'B+':1,
        'B':0 };
    return r[grade] || 0;
}

```

```
}
```

A.6. A.6 PDF Processing & Audit Ingest

What it does. Validates file, parses text, extracts courses, and writes an audit ingest (without auto-adding courses). This design ensures that every ingest is traceable and reversible.

Listing 7: End-to-end processing and audit record

```
async processPdfTranscript(email: string, file: Express.Multer.File)
{
  if (!file || !file.buffer) throw new Error('Uploaded file buffer
    is missing.');
```

```
  if (file.size > 10 * 1024 * 1024) throw new BadRequestException('
    File size exceeds 10MB');
```

```
  const user = await this.prisma.user.upsert({ where: { email },
    update: {}, create: { email } });
```

```
  const fileHash = this.sha256(file.buffer);
```

```
  const parsed = await pdfParse(file.buffer);
```

```
  const text = parsed?.text || "";
```

```
  if (!text || text.length < 20) return { ok: false, message: "Could
    not read transcript text." };
```

```
  const { eligible, nonEligible } = this.extractCoursesFromText(text
    );
```

```
  await this.prisma.transcriptIngest.create({
    data: {
      userId: user.id, fileName: file.originalname, fileHash,
```

```
    parsedJson: { eligible, nonEligible, textLength: text.length,
      processedAt: new Date().toISOString() },
    addedCount: 0
  },
});

return {
  ok: true, added: 0, updated: 0, total: 0,
  summary: {
    totalCourses: eligible.length + nonEligible.length,
    eligible: eligible.length, nonEligible: nonEligible.length,
    confidenceBreakdown: {
      high: eligible.filter(c => c.confidence === 'high').length,
      medium: eligible.filter(c => c.confidence === 'medium').
        length,
      low: eligible.filter(c => c.confidence === 'low').length,
    },
  },
  eligibleCourses: eligible.map(c => ({ code: c.code, grade: c.
    grade, title: c.title, confidence: c.confidence })),
  nonEligibleCourses: nonEligible.map(c => ({ code: c.code, grade:
    c.grade, title: c.title, reason: c.reason })),
};
}
```

A.7. A.7 Adding Selected Courses

What it does. Adds or upgrades user courses based on rank (keeps the best grade per course). This step is invoked from the frontend after the user confirms the eligible courses they want to expose.

Listing 8: Add/upgrade selected courses with grade ranking

```
async addSelectedCourses(email: string, courses: { code: string;
  grade: string }[]) {
  const user = await this.prisma.user.findUnique({ where: { email },
    select: { id: true } });
  if (!user) throw new NotFoundException('User not found');

  let added = 0, updated = 0;
  for (const c of courses) {
    const code = c.code.toUpperCase(), grade = c.grade.toUpperCase()
    ;
    try {
      const existing = await this.prisma.userCourse.findUnique({
        where: { userId_courseCode: { userId: user.id, courseCode:
          code } } });
      if (existing) {
        if (this.getGradeRank(grade) > this.getGradeRank(existing.
          grade)) {
          await this.prisma.userCourse.update({ where: {
            userId_courseCode: { userId: user.id, courseCode: code
              } }, data: { grade } });
          updated++;
        }
      } else {
        await this.prisma.userCourse.create({ data: { userId: user.
          id, courseCode: code, grade } });
        added++;
      }
    } catch (e) {
      // The loop continues so a bad course does not block the rest.
    }
  }
  return { ok: true, added, updated, total: added + updated };
}
```

```
}
```

A.8. A.8 Risks and Assumptions

The transcript module assumes that transcripts are exported as text-based PDFs from AUI's system and that the overall layout is stable. Changes to fonts, line-breaking, or grading columns may require adjusting the regex patterns. In a production environment, the module would also be paired with stricter authentication (to ensure the uploader is the transcript owner) and rate limiting to avoid abuse.

B. Appendix B: Frontend API Client and State (Vite + TypeScript)

This appendix breaks down the typed fetch layer that wires the UI to backend routes, and briefly describes the state management strategy used on the frontend.

B.1. B.1 Structure & Safe JSON

What it does. Base URL resolution and robust JSON parsing to avoid runtime crashes.

Listing 9: API base and safe JSON parsing

```
const API_BASE = (import.meta.env.VITE_SWAP_API_URL as string |
  undefined) ?? "";

const safeJson = async (response: Response) => {
  const text = await response.text();
  try { return JSON.parse(text); } catch { return null; }
};

export const getApiBase = () => API_BASE;
```

B.2. B.2 Users & Onboarding

What it does. Upsert user profile and save onboarding selections.

Listing 10: Users and onboarding endpoints

```
export const upsertUser = async (payload: { email: string; name?:
  string; university?: string; timezone?: string; image?: string;
}) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { ok: false as const };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/users/upsert`, {
      method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json"
    }, body: JSON.stringify(payload),
    });
    return { ok: response.ok, data: await safeJson(response) };
  } catch { return { ok: false as const }; }
};

export const saveOnboarding = async (email: string, name: string |
  undefined, skills: string[], courses: string[], interests?: Array
  <{ type: "skill" | "course"; name: string }>) => {
  const payload = {
    email, name,
    skills: skills.map((n) => ({ name: n })),
    courses: courses.map((code) => ({ code, grade: "A" })),
    interests: interests ?? [],
  };
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/users/onboarding`, {
    method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
    body: JSON.stringify(payload),
  });
  const data = await response.json().catch(() => null);
  return { ok: response.ok, data };
};
```

```
};
```

B.3. B.3 Requests & Sessions

What it does. Request lifecycle (create/accept/decline), inbox/sent listing, session completion/scheduling.

Listing 11: Requests and sessions endpoints

```
export const createRequest = async (fromEmail: string, toEmail:
  string, courseCode: string, minutes: number, note?: string) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { ok: false as const };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/requests`, {
      method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json"
        },
      body: JSON.stringify({ fromEmail, toEmail, courseCode, minutes
        , note }),
    });
    return { ok: response.ok, data: await safeJson(response) };
  } catch { return { ok: false as const }; }
};

export const listInbox = async (email: string) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return [] as any[];
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/requests?inbox=1&email
      =${encodeURIComponent(email)}`);
    return (await safeJson(response)) ?? [];
  } catch { return [] as any[]; }
};

export const listSent = async (email: string) => {
```

```
if (!API_BASE) return [] as any[];
try {
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/requests?sent=1&email=${encodeURIComponent(email)}`);
  return (await safeJson(response)) ?? [];
} catch { return [] as any[]; }
};

export const acceptRequest = async (id: string, actingEmail: string)
=> {
  if (!API_BASE) return { ok: false as const };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/requests/${id}/accept`, {
      method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
      body: JSON.stringify({ actingEmail })
    });
    return { ok: response.ok, data: await safeJson(response) };
  } catch { return { ok: false as const }; }
};

export const declineRequest = async (id: string, actingEmail: string)
=> {
  if (!API_BASE) return { ok: false as const };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/requests/${id}/decline`, {
      method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
      body: JSON.stringify({ actingEmail })
    });
    return { ok: response.ok, data: await safeJson(response) };
  } catch { return { ok: false as const }; }
};
```

```

};

export const completeSession = async (id: string, actingEmail:
  string) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { ok: false as const };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/sessions/${id}/done`,
      {
        method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json"
          }, body: JSON.stringify({ actingEmail })
      });
    const data = await response.json().catch(() => null);
    return { ok: response.ok, data };
  } catch { return { ok: false as const }; }
};

export const scheduleSession = async (id: string, actingEmail:
  string, startAt: string) => {
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/sessions/${id}/schedule
    `, {
    method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
    body: JSON.stringify({ actingEmail, startAt })
  });
  const data = await response.json().catch(() => null);
  return { ok: response.ok, data };
};

```

B.4. B.4 Chat & Search

What it does. Thread creation, listing, message paging; teacher discovery and skill suggestions.

Listing 12: Chat and discovery endpoints

```
export const ensureThread = async (userEmail: string, otherEmail:
  string) => {
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/chat/thread`, {
    method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
    body: JSON.stringify({ userEmail, otherEmail }),
  });
  return response.json();
};

export const listThreads = async (email: string) => {
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/chat/threads?email=${
    encodeURIComponent(email)}`);
  return response.json();
};

export const listMessages = async (threadId: string, after?: string)
  => {
  const url = `${API_BASE}/chat/messages?threadId=${
    encodeURIComponent(threadId)}${after ? `&after=${
    encodeURIComponent(after)}` : ""}`;
  const response = await fetch(url);
  return response.json();
};

export const sendMessage = async (threadId: string, senderEmail:
  string, text: string) => {
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/chat/messages`, {
    method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json" },
    body: JSON.stringify({ threadId, senderEmail, text }),
  });
  return response.json();
};
```

```

};

export const searchTeachers = async (options: { skill?: string;
  course?: string }) => {
  const params = new URLSearchParams();
  if (options.skill) params.set("skill", options.skill);
  if (options.course) params.set("course", options.course);
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/search/teachers?${params
    .toString()}`);
  return response.ok ? response.json() : [];
};

export const suggestSkills = async (query: string) => {
  const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/search/skills?q=${
    encodeURIComponent(query)}`);
  return response.ok ? response.json() : [];
};

```

B.5. B.5 Wallet & Ratings

What it does. Token/ledger retrieval and full rating flow with categories.

Listing 13: Wallet and ratings endpoints

```

export const getLedger = async (email: string) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { balance: 0, entries: [] };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/ledger?email=${
      encodeURIComponent(email)}`);
    return (await safeJson(response)) ?? { balance: 0, entries: [] };
  } catch { return { balance: 0, entries: [] }; }
};

```

```
export const getTokens = async (email: string) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { tokens: 0, entries: [] };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/tokens?email=${
      encodeURIComponent(email)}`);
    return (await safeJson(response)) ?? { tokens: 0, entries: [] };
  } catch { return { tokens: 0, entries: [] }; }
};

export const getUserRatingStats = async (userId: string, category?:
  "skill" | "course") => {
  if (!API_BASE) return null;
  try {
    const suffix = category ? `?category=${category}` : "";
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/ratings/user/${
      encodeURIComponent(userId)}/stats${suffix}`);
    return response.ok ? response.json() : null;
  } catch { return null; }
};

export const getUserRatings = async (userId: string, category?: "
  skill" | "course") => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { success: false as const };
  try {
    const suffix = category ? `?category=${category}` : "";
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/ratings/user/${
      encodeURIComponent(userId)}${suffix}`);
    const data = await safeJson(response);
    return data ?? { success: false as const };
  } catch { return { success: false as const }; }
};
```

```
export const createRating = async (ratingData: {
  raterId: string; ratedId: string; sessionId?: string; rating:
    number; review?: string;
  category: "skill" | "course"; skillOrCourse: string;
}) => {
  if (!API_BASE) return { ok: false as const };
  try {
    const response = await fetch(`${API_BASE}/ratings`, {
      method: "POST", headers: { "Content-Type": "application/json"
        }, body: JSON.stringify(ratingData),
    });
    const data = await response.json().catch(() => null);
    return { ok: response.ok, data };
  } catch { return { ok: false as const }; }
};
```

C. Appendix C: Application Screenshots

This appendix documents the main user-facing screens of the Swap-App single-page application (swap-landing). The goal is to provide a visual reference for the landing page, authentication flows, onboarding, dashboard, and core tutoring workflows (search, requests, sessions, chat, ratings).

C.1. C.1 Landing Page and Marketing Shell

Figure 8: Landing hero section presenting the “Exchange your skills and knowledge without fees” value proposition, with CTAs to learn more about Swap and join for free.

C.2. C.2 Authentication and Entry Points

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `swap-kohl.vercel.app/register`. The page is titled "JOIN SWAP" and features a registration form. On the left, there is a promotional section with the heading "Exchange knowledge with peers worldwide" and three bullet points: "Share what you know and request the skills you want in minutes.", "Let Swap's smart matching connect you with the right partner.", and "Use built-in scheduling, transcripts, and ratings to stay organised." Below this, it states "2,500+ STUDENTS ALREADY INSIDE" and "150+ SKILLS AVAILABLE TO SWAP".

The registration form on the right includes the following fields and options:

- Sign up with Microsoft** (button)
- OR USE YOUR EMAIL** (text)
- UNIVERSITY EMAIL** (input field containing "your-email@student.university.edu")
- FIRST NAME** (input field containing "First name")
- LAST NAME** (input field containing "Last name")
- DATE OF BIRTH** (optional) (input field containing "mm/dd/yyyy")
- PASSWORD** (input field containing "Create a secure pass*")
- CONFIRM PASSWORD** (input field containing "Re-enter password")
- I agree to the [Terms](#) and [Privacy Policy](#)
- CREATE ACCOUNT** (button)

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the search bar, several application icons, and the system tray with the date and time: "ENG 2:09 AM FR 11/28/2025".

Figure 9: Registration page for new students, highlighting university email, profile fields, and terms acceptance, with optional Microsoft SSO.

Figure 10: Sign-in page for returning users, offering Google/Microsoft SSO and classic email + password login.

C.3. C.3 Onboarding and Profile (to be added)

Figure 11: Onboarding step 1: capturing core profile details.

Figure 12: Onboarding step 2 : Capturing core user interests.

The screenshot displays the profile page of a user on the SWAP platform. The browser address bar shows the URL `swap-kohl.vercel.app/profile`. The navigation menu includes **Dashboard**, **Find a Swap**, **Requests**, **Sessions 2**, **Community Chat**, **Ratings**, **Profile** (active), and a **SIGN OUT** button. The profile summary features four key statistics: **SKILLS YOU CAN TEACH: 1**, **COURSES ACED: 1**, **AVAILABLE TOKENS: 2**, and **SESSIONS COMPLETED: 5**. The **Skills you can teach** section shows a single skill, **Chess**, with a form for editing its name (e.g., "Chess") and level (Advanced). The **Courses you aced** section lists **COM1301**. At the bottom, a taskbar displays system information: 3°C, 4:26 AM, and 11/28/2025.

Figure 13: Profile page (example) showing basic identity, skills, and courses that drive search and matching.

The screenshot displays a user profile page in a web application. The browser address bar shows the URL `swap-kohl.vercel.app/profile`. The navigation menu includes 'Dashboard', 'Find a Swap', 'Requests', 'Sessions 2', 'Community Chat', 'Ratings', and 'Profile'. A green button '+ ADD SKILL' is located at the top. Below the navigation, there are two main sections: 'Import from transcript' and 'Teaching availability'. The 'Import from transcript' section contains a text input field labeled 'Choose PDF' and a green button '+ UPLOAD & SCAN'. The 'Teaching availability' section shows a slot for 'Chess' on 'THURSDAY' from '13:00 - 14:00'. A green button '+ ADD TIME SLOT' is at the bottom of the availability section. The bottom of the image shows a Windows taskbar with various application icons and system information like '4:27 AM 11/28/2025'.

Figure 14: Profile details with transcript scanner module and teaching availability.

C.4. C.4 Dashboard and Progress Overview

Figure 15: Dashboard welcome view summarizing next session, tokens, completed swaps, and quick navigation actions.

Figure 16: Dashboard metrics and activity view with total sessions, learning hours, weekly flow, and latest activity.

C.5. C.5 Requests, Sessions, and Scheduling

The screenshot displays the 'Requests' page of the SWAP application. The page features a navigation bar with the following items: Dashboard, Find a Swap, Requests (active), Sessions (2), Community Chat, Ratings, Profile, a notification badge with '2', a user initial 'Y', and a 'SIGN OUT' button. The main content area is titled 'REQUESTS' and includes the heading 'Keep every swap on track' with the subtext 'Review new invitations, respond to pending matches, and stay close to the conversations that matter.' Below this is a call-to-action: 'Need a new partner? Browse the matches page to send a fresh request.' The summary section contains four cards: 'TOTAL INBOX' with a value of 3, 'TOTAL SENT' with a value of 0, 'PENDING' with a value of 0, and 'ACCEPTED' with a value of 3. At the bottom of the summary section, there are filter buttons for 'All', 'Pending', 'Accepted', and 'Declined', along with a 'CLEAR ANSWERED' button. The browser's address bar shows 'swap-kohl.vercel.app/requests' and the Windows taskbar at the bottom indicates the time as 2:13 AM on 11/28/2025.

Figure 17: Requests summary page showing total inbox, sent, pending, and accepted requests for the student.

Figure 18: Inbox view with detailed incoming requests (course, duration, requester) and their current status.

Figure 19: Sessions overview page aggregating total sessions, scheduled swaps, completed sessions, and total hours.

The screenshot displays the SWAP application interface. At the top, the navigation bar includes the SWAP logo, a search bar, and menu items: Dashboard, Find a Swap, Requests, Sessions (2), Community Chat, Ratings, and Profile. On the right, there are notification icons for 2 messages and a 'Y' icon, along with a 'SIGN OUT' button.

The main content area features two session detail cards:

- Chess:** Student: mamoun tantooui, email: elaraki48@gmail.com. Status: NEEDS SCHEDULING. Duration: 60 minutes. Type: Online. A yellow banner prompts: "Pick a date and time so both of you are aligned." Action buttons: JOIN TEAMS MEETING, MESSAGE, SCHEDULE.
- COM1301:** Student: Mehdi Soulaïman, email: topmind.badconnexion@gmail.com. Status: SCHEDULED. Duration: 60 minutes. Date: 12/1/2025. Time: 11:00 AM. Type: Online. An upward arrow icon is visible on the right side of the card.

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the search bar, task view, and various application icons. The system tray on the right indicates the language is set to ENG FR, the date is 11/28/2025, and the time is 2:16 AM.

Figure 20: Session detail cards showing session type (online/face-to-face), schedule controls, and quick access to Teams and chat.

C.6. C.6 Search, Matching, and Discovery

Figure 21: Search and discovery page (“Find a Swap”) with headline metrics and filters by skills or courses.

The screenshot displays the SWAP application interface for finding tutors. The search results are for the course COM1301. Two tutors are listed:

- ahmed hmed** (test20@gmail.com): 5.0 rating, 1 rating. Course excellence: COM1301, GRADE A. Note: This member has not published availability yet. Actions: MESSAGE, SEND REQUEST.
- younes soulaiman** (topmind.youness@gmail.com): 5.0 rating, 1 rating. Course excellence: COM1301, GRADE A. Available time slots: Monday (10:00 - 11:00, Online), Wednesday (09:00 - 10:00, Face-to-face). Action: SEND REQUEST.

The interface also shows a navigation bar with options like Dashboard, Find a Swap, Requests, Sessions (2), Community Chat, Ratings, Profile, and SIGN OUT. The bottom of the image shows a Windows taskbar with various application icons and system information.

Figure 22: Search results for COM1301, showing available tutors, their grades, time slots, and quick actions to message or send a request.

C.7. C.7 Community Chat and Feedback

Figure 23: Community chat interface with a list of conversations on the left and a message pane on the right.

Figure 24: Ratings and feedback hub summarizing average rating and distribution across sessions.